

NIR spectroscopy application for assessment of the PDO Asiago cheese variety

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Asiago PDO cheese can be produced as *Pressato*, with two months of ripening, or *Allevo*, with a maturation of more than six months to favor stronger and composite aroma. Recently, to catch new market segments, cheese factories have started to produce a new type of Asiago named *fresh Allevo* with a shorter ripening time. Thus, to avoid frauds, there is a need to develop rapid methods for cheese variety assessment. For this purpose, three raw entire milk bulks were processed according to the PDO Asiago specification to produce *Pressato* (2-mo of ripening, $n = 28$), *fresh Allevo* (4-mo of ripening, $n = 30$), or *Allevo* (6-mo of ripening, $n = 20$). NIR spectral data were recorded in triplicate by a Foss DS2500 scanning monochromator (Foss NIR-System, Hillerød, DK) on cheese ground samples. To assess the correct classification of cheese variety, a PLS-DA (PLS Toolbox, Eigen. Res., Inc., USA) and a related confusion matrix were performed. The reliability of the discriminative model was assessed by a set of statistic metrics including the Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC) as reported in Bisutti et al. (2019). Based on the outcomes of the confusion matrix, the discriminant capacity of NIR spectral data was satisfactory for *Pressato* (MCC = 0.94); meanwhile, it was less accurate for *fresh Allevo* (MCC = 0.81) and *Allevo* (MCC = 0.84). Moreover, 3.3% of *Pressato* and 6.6% of *Allevo* samples were misclassified as *fresh Allevo* suggesting that the complex set of biochemical markers and the hard texture of Asiago (*Allevo*) is achieved beyond four months of ripening. Summarizing, NIR spectroscopy can be a useful tool to discriminate PDO Asiago cheese variety even if the authentication of the more ripened varieties could be improved if they differ over two months as period of maturation.

Keywords: Asiago PDO, cheese variety, NIR spectroscopy, PLS-DA, Matthews correlation coefficient

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